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APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS IN LABOR EDUCATION

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When starting to study the methodology of labor education, first of all, we will get acquainted with the broader meaning of the concept of method, that is, it consists of a set of methods and principles. By means of these methods and principles, the Master provides students with professional knowledge aimed at a certain goal, forms the necessary training and skills from them, strengthens them, checks the level of mastery, and students actively use these training and skills. and consciously acquires professional skills.

Choosing the right methods is an important issue. The teaching method, first of all, is determined by the goals and tasks of teaching, the conscious and thorough assimilation of students' knowledge, training and skills, the development of creative activity and independence in them, and the tasks.

One of the important requirements for the organization of labor education is the variety of methods and their serving a specific purpose.

The logical method used in education is the common and most common method for all secondary schools of analysis.

Verbal presentation of educational material is a coherent presentation of real material. Analyzing and proving the facts plays an important role in this. The teacher uses his own writings and calculations in his speech, sometimes clarifying

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his character.

When explaining the material, the teacher should rely on the level of theoretical knowledge of the students, their experiences gained in the process of industrial education. For this purpose, he should thoroughly familiarize himself with the special technology course, i.e.: material science, drawing program, and attend these classes at all times.

In labor education, the issue of showing labor principles has a special place. This is one of the main exhibition materials of teaching. In addition, the teacher of labor education requires not only high professional qualifications, but also sufficient pedagogical experience in order to be able to demonstrate labor principles and processes.

It is also necessary to emphasize that the demonstrated labor principles and processes must be visible to all students. It is necessary for students to understand well what actions and in what order they should be used to form the same working principles.

To practical methods:

- a) exercises.
- b) laboratory-practical work.
- c) includes working with technical references, literature and documents.

Practice consists of consciously and repeatedly repeating work actions to form students and gradually turn them into skills. Exercises are the main method of labor and production education. In the process of exercises, it is necessary to pay

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attention to the quality of the performance of labor and craft methods, to carefully monitor the students' activities.

Practical work in the laboratory can be applied in the training of qualified workers in various professions and specialties.

It is possible to achieve educational and educational success in the performance of independent production tasks by students only if the following conditions exist:

Pupils should understand well the content of the work to be done and clearly imagine the order of its execution.

Students should know what equipment should be used for the task, their structure and operation characteristics, how to adapt them to this mode, and measures to prevent malfunctions.

The planning of labor and vocational education consists in the precise organization of the educational process, which should fully correspond to the didactic principles and the labor and training program of the students.

During the planning of work and professional education, the following documents are drawn up:

Calendar-subject plan for half a year, perspective on work.

A list of educational production works planned for half a year or a year for each type of work.

The collective subject plan of sciences of the natural-scientific category: it should reflect inter-discipline connections (it will be drawn up semi-annually).

Here is a lesson plan with a detailed synopsis on this topic.

The advanced work experience of some schools, educational-production combines,

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vocational and technical educational institutions confirms that the planning documents for labor and vocational education should be drawn up taking into account all the principles of the educational process. Ignoring any of these principles in planning can cause serious defects in the work of a labor teacher.

Used literature

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2. K.D. Davlatov. "Labor and vocational education, career choice, theory and methodology of labor education" Tashkent, Labor 1994.

